

Effects of improver level, yeast level and work input on dough density profiles

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I. Introduction

The dynamic dough density (DDD) system, first developed by Campbell *et al.* (2001), provides a useful way of visualising the evolution of the dough density under conditions imitating proving. This method allows the determination of the maximum dough expansion (minimum dough density, MDD) that can be achieved during this stage.

An improvement of the method that permits additional assessment of the dough density evolution in conditions imitating the first stage of oven spring is being developed. While the density is recorded, the temperature of the dough is increased from 38°C (proving temperature) to 60°C, thereby covering the temperature range over which starch gelatinisation begins. As the temperature increases, the dough density decreases at an accelerated rate until reaching a minimum that is normally lower than the proving MDD. Thus, from the enhanced DDD method, two important parameters can be extracted: minimum dough density during proving and minimum dough density during temperature ramping. It is expected that both parameters can provide an accurate indication of the maximum expansion during proving and during oven spring.

In order to determine an appropriate base formulation of dough, and to assess the effectiveness and sensitivity of the enhanced DDD method, the effects of both lean and fatted improver level, yeast level and amount of mixing work input on the density profile were evaluated.

II. Materials and methods

2.1 Dynamic dough density system

For the experiments, four density measurement systems were installed. A single density measurement system comprised an analytical balance (Ohaus Adventurer 65 g / 0.1 mg) with a jacketed beaker, a double-cup sample holder, a J-type thermocouple wire and a six-port valve (Omnifit, UK). The four valves were connected to two common water baths. One water bath was maintained at 40.5° C and the other at 85°C. The double-cup, equipped with an anti-float cup was used to weigh the sample both in air and immersed in the liquid (xylene) contained in the beaker. The thermocouple junction was placed below the double cup and towards the radial centre of the beaker. The changing weight of the dough piece and the xylene temperature were recorded every 10 seconds into a spreadsheet by a computer programme written in LabVIEW 7.0 (National Instruments, UK). The computer collected the data from the balances' parallel ports (baud rate 9600, data bits 8, no parity and stop bits 1) and from the PCI-4351 data acquisition device (National Instruments, UK) connected to

the thermocouples. The first water bath (40.5°C) kept the xylene temperature to ~38°C simulating the proving stage. When the minimum dough density was achieved, the valve was immediately switched and the second water bath warmed up the system. In about 12 minutes the xylene temperature increased from 38° to 60°C, thus simulating the oven spring stage and yielding the second minimum dough density.

Doughs were mixed in a Tweedy 1 mixer. Immediately after mixing, the dough was rolled flat onto a board to a uniform thickness of ~1.0 cm. Using a cylindrical cutter with an internal diameter of 2.3 cm, four samples from the sheeted dough were taken. They were then simultaneously swirled around for 30 seconds in spherical-bottomed glass beakers, in order to even out any irregularity and slightly firm the dough sample surface. The four samples were then placed in each of the DDD systems. The time elapsed between end of mixing and the first dough density recording was on average 4.5 min. For each DDD curve, the MDD during proving and during temperature ramping were obtained. The DDD curves shown below represent the average of four simultaneous experiments.

2.2 Effect of lean and fatted improver on dough density

Doughs were prepared with 400 g of strong flour (Rank Hovis, UK), 15 g of dry yeast (Puratos, Belgium), 6.4 g of salt (Tesco, UK) and 248 g of water. Lean and fatted improver were added in amounts of 0.75%, 0.875%, 1.0%, 1.125% and 1.25%. Doughs were mixed until they reached 40 kJ/kg of work input.

2.3 Effect of yeast level on dough density

The effect of yeast level was investigated by adding 1.5%, 3%, 4%, 4.5%, 5% and 6% of dry yeast to 400 g of flour, 4.4 g of fatted improver, 6.4 g of salt and 240 g of water. It was observed that with the increasing amount of yeast added and the associated higher solids content, the dough became tougher; therefore, the actual effects of yeast level on dough density could be altered or masked by the lesser amount of available water for flour development. Thus, another set of experiments taking into account both the amount of solids and water were conducted. The flour moisture and the yeast moisture were 13.48% and 4.37%, respectively. Taking 6 g of yeast, 400 g of flour and 240 g of water as the base formulation, water and solids contents were estimated. These values (294.2 g of water and 351.8 g of dry solids) were kept constant to calculate the amounts of flour and water to be added in the other formulations. Table 1 shows the formulations calculated from the mass balances. Fatted improver (4.4 g) and salt (6.4 g) were also added. Doughs were mixed to 40 kJ/kg of work input.

Yeast (g)	Flour (g)	Water (g)
6	400.0	240.0
12	393.4	240.6
16	388.9	241.1
18	386.7	241.3
20	384.5	241.5
24	380.1	241.9

Table 1. Amounts of flour and water added for balanced formulations

2.4 Effect of mixing work input on dough density

Doughs formulated with 400 g of flour, 248 g of water, 16 g of dry yeast, 4.4 g of fatted improver and 6.4 g of salt were mixed in the Tweedy mixer to 30, 35, 40, 45, 50 and 55 kJ/kg of work input.

III. Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of lean and fatted improver on dough density

Figure 1 shows the DDD curves and temperature profiles of the samples formulated with lean and fatted improver. The doughs made with lean improver produced jagged DDD curves which indicated that these doughs were prone to sudden gas release. By contrast, the doughs formulated with fatted improver produced smooth DDD curves and the time to reach the MDD was shorter (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Dynamic dough density curves and temperature ramping profiles of doughs mixed with different levels of lean improver (thin lines) and fatted improver (thick lines)

Figures 3 and 4 suggest that the dough density during mixing was influenced by the amount of fatted or lean improver; a higher level of improver seemed to give a lower initial density, indicating a higher gas content. The effect of the lean improver on dough density immediately after mixing (Figure 4) was less clear than that of the fatted improver (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Detail of minimum dough density values - lean improver (thin lines) and fatted improver (thick lines)

Figure 3. Dough density values of doughs formulated with fatted improver immediately after mixing

Figure 4. Dough density values of doughs formulated with lean improver immediately after mixing

Figure 5 suggests that the fatted and lean improver gave opposite effects on the MDD (although the scatter in the data allows only tentative conclusions at this stage). For the 0.75 - 1.125% range of lean improver, it was observed that increasing doses tended to result in lower MDD values. By contrast, the use of higher amounts of fatted improver slightly reduced the dough expansion capability. This might be due to fat interference with the development of gluten. An interesting observation is that as the level of fatted improver increased, the difference between MDD during proving and MDD during temperature ramping appeared to become larger. The use of higher levels of fatted improver might encourage a better additional expansion during oven spring, offsetting the lower expansion during proving. This effect, however, was not evident with the lean improver. The MDD during temperature ramping for 1% of lean improver was an erroneous value as the temperature ramping was slightly delayed. This highlights the sensitivity of the oven spring MDD to the time at which the temperature ramping is performed. In addition, it has been observed that when the difference between proving MDD and oven spring MDD is very small, the second MDD is likely to be simply missed out once the dough temperature is being ramped. A level equal or higher than 1% of fatted improver would be advantageous for use throughout the MDD method development.

3.2 Effect of yeast level on dough density

Figures 6 and 8 show the DDD curves for the doughs mixed with different yeast levels for the set of experiments not considering mass balance and the set of experiments considering mass balance, respectively. Both figures indicate that the higher the yeast level used in the formulation, the lower the initial dough density, because the yeast starts to produce gas more quickly.

Figure 5. Effect of lean and fatted improver level on minimum dough density values during proving and temperature ramping

Figure 6. Dynamic dough density curves and temperature ramping profiles of doughs mixed with different yeast levels for the set of experiments not considering mass balance

Figure 7. Detail of minimum dough density values for the set of experiments not considering mass balance

Figure 8. Dynamic dough density curves and temperature ramping profiles of doughs mixed with different yeast levels for the set of experiments considering mass balance

Figures 7 and 9 show the enlarged detail of the DDD curves near MDD for the experiments without mass balance and with mass balance, respectively. They both indicated that increasing yeast levels produce a shorter proving time but render a poorer dough expansion. The higher MDD may be a consequence of a greater gas release because of the accelerated rate of CO₂ production, dilution of the gluten through the higher levels of yeast, or altered dough rheological properties through higher levels of yeast metabolic properties.

Figure 9. Detail of minimum dough density values for the set of experiments considering mass balance

The effects of yeast level on proving and temperature ramping MDDs for the formulation without mass balance and the formulation with mass balance followed a similar trend (Figure 10). In both cases, a yeast level of 3% produced the lowest MDD values. It is recommended to allow for corrections of water and solids contents in a formulation in which an ingredient is to be varied in considerable amounts. It was noticeable in both type of formulations that the use of higher yeast levels caused the proving MDD and the temperature ramping MDD to converge. Further experiments should be devised to explain this phenomenon.

Figure 11 shows that as yeast level increased, the time to reach the MDD during proving decreased, with the balanced formulations needing a slightly longer time than the non-balanced ones. Figure 12 highlights the linear relationship between yeast level and the inverse of the proving time to reach MDD. The selection of the yeast level to be used for the DDD experiments should be based on a trade-off between a short proving time and a considerable difference between proving MDD and oven spring MDD. A yeast level of 3-4% is recommended.

Figure 10. Effect of yeast level on minimum dough density values during proving and temperature ramping for the non-balanced and balanced formulations

Figure 11. Effect of yeast level on the time to reach minimum dough density during proving

Figure 12. Regression lines between yeast level and the inverse of proving tie to reach minimum dough density showing coefficients of determination for balanced and non-balanced formulations

3.3 Effect of mixing work input on dough density

Figure 13 shows the DDD results of doughs mixed to different work inputs. In this case, the proving time to reach MDD was not significantly different. Because the dough mixed until 55 kJ/kg of work input produced a point of sudden gas release (figure 13), this experiment was terminated. Figure 14 illustrates an enlarged portion of the MDD values. Except for the 40 kJ/kg data-point, it was observed that a prolonged mixing resulted in an increasing additional dough expansion during temperature ramping. Figure 15 shows this effect. Also, the longer the bread dough was mixed, giving better gluten development, the better the dough expansion during proving and temperature ramping. Thus, it is likely that, for this dough formulation, a mixing work input close to 50 kJ/kg achieved the best expansion. However, a slightly longer mixing time (55 kJ/kg) resulted in a sticky overmixed dough.

An important detail concerning the DDD method development is that the standard deviation of the MDD values during temperature ramping were normally higher than the standard deviation of the proving MDD values.

Figure 13. Dynamic dough density curves and temperature ramping profiles of doughs mixed with different work inputs

Figure 14. Detail of minimum dough density values for different mixing work inputs

Figure 15. Effect of mixing work input on minimum dough density values during proving and temperature ramping. Bars indicate \pm standard deviation of the sample

A level of 1% of fatted improver and 3.5% of yeast should be used in formulations for the DDD method development. This provides a smooth DDD curve, a relatively short proving time and a considerable difference between proving MDD and oven spring MDD. The time at which the temperature is ramped affects greatly the oven spring MDD value; further trials are needed to determine the best time at which to commence temperature ramping. Formulations considering water compensation generate different results from their counterparts without compensation. Thus, when an ingredient is to be varied in considerable amounts, it is recommended to allow for corrections of water and solids contents.

IV. Conclusions

The use of fatted and lean improver affected the dough density in different ways. Lower dough densities could be achieved by using lean improver although the jagged DDD profile obtained may not be adequate for the DDD method development. By contrast, the addition of fatted improver produced smooth DDD curves. As the level of fatted improver increased in the formulations, a better additional expansion during temperature ramping was produced. Thus, fatted improver may not be suitable for use in base formulations where the effects of added ingredients are to be assessed. A higher amount of yeast level shortened proving time but undermined the dough expansion capability. Besides, the additional expansion produced during temperature ramping diminished with increased amounts of yeast. A prolonged mixing time clearly improved the dough expansion. The higher the mixing work input (up to 50 kJ/kg),

the better the dough rise during the temperature ramping stage. Finally, the time at which the temperature is ramped exerts a critical influence on the second MDD value.

V. References

1. Campbell GM, Herrero Sanchez R, Payo Rodriguez R, and Merchan ML (2001) "Measurement of dynamic dough density and effect of surfactants and flour type on aeration during mixing and gas retention during proving." *Cereal Chemistry* 78(3):272-277.

VI. Appendix

The effects of lean and fatted improver on dough density values were analysed again. In this case, lean and fatted improvers were added in amounts of 0%, 0.25%, 0.50%, 0.75%, 1.0%, and 1.25%. Each curve represents the average of two experiments. All these tests were run on the same day.

Figure 16 shows the DDD curves for the formulations using lean improver. The shape of these curves differed from the ones previously found in 3.3. Stronger break points of gas release were observed at the four lower levels of improver addition. Immediately following these events, the temperature was ramped. The DDD curve produced with 1.25% of lean improver (Figure 17) presented a smoother curve and was able to reach a minimum dough density without the sudden points of gas release.

Figure 16. Dynamic dough density curves and temperature ramping profiles of doughs mixed with different levels of lean improver

Figure 17. Detail of minimum density values of doughs mixed with different levels of lean improver

Figure 18 shows the DDD results of the formulations with fatted improver. The addition of fatted improver had a substantial effect on the dough expansion / gas retention (0% versus 0.25%). However, the subsequent addition of fatted improver (0.5%, 0.75%, 1%, and 1.25%) (Figure 19) did not improve considerably the gas retention capability.

Figure 20 illustrates the effects of the lean and fatted improver on the minimum dough density values. As the lean improver level increased, a decrease in MDD values was observed. Figure 21 presents the results of Figure 20 and the results from the previous experiment (3.1). The main difference between these experiments was the MDD values for the lean improver. This was due to the presence of strong break points in their DDD curves which was a phenomenon not observed in the first experiment. These break points prompted earlier temperature ramping, and thus, the MDD values were higher in the second experiment. The use of lean improver might not be yielding a dough sufficiently resistant to further manipulation (sampling). Hence, the similarity in curve shape between 0%, and 0.25% of lean improver (Figure 17).

Figure 18. Dynamic dough density curves and temperature ramping profiles of doughs mixed with different levels of fatted improver

Figure 19. Detail of minimum density values of doughs mixed with different levels of fatted improver

Figure 20. Effect of lean and fatted improver level on minimum dough density values during proving and temperature ramping

Figure 21. Effect of lean and fatted improver level on minimum dough density values during proving and temperature ramping for the two sets of experiments